

A Preliminary Checklist of the Myxomycetes of Shenandoah National Park

Steven L. Stephenson¹ and Barbara C. Stephenson²

¹ Department of Biological Sciences, University of Arkansas, Fayetteville, Arkansas 72701

² 30 Laura Jean Court, Waynesboro, Virginia 22980

E-mail: slsteph@uark.edu

Received: 21 April 2025

Accepted for publication: 20 May 2025

Published: 25 May 2025

Editor: Carlos Rojas

Abstract: A checklist is provided of all species of myxomycetes known to occur in Shenandoah National Park in Virginia. The majority of these were recorded during a survey carried out in 2024. The records reported herein are based on specimens that developed in the field under natural conditions and also specimens that appeared in moist chamber cultures. Prior to this study, only 10 species in nine genera were listed on MycoPortal as having been collected or observed in the park. The survey in 2024 yielded a total of 69 additional species in 26 additional genera. This brought the number of genera and the number of species known from the park to 79 and 35, respectively. However, many additional species undoubtedly occur in the park but have yet to be collected or observed.

Keywords: biodiversity, Blue Ridge Mountains, slime molds, Virginia

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Introduction

Shenandoah National Park encompasses the northern portion of the Blue Ridge Mountains in Virginia. The park is long and narrow, with the Shenandoah Valley to the west and the piedmont region of Virginia to the east. The main park road (Skyline Drive) extends for about 170 km along the ridgeline of the Blue Ridge Mountains. Almost 40% of the park's land (322 km²) has been designated as wilderness areas and is protected as part of the National Wilderness Preservation System of the United States. The maximum elevation in the park is 1235 m at the summit of Hawksbill Mountain. Forests at higher elevations in the park range from mixed oak to mixed hardwoods, with small populations of red spruce and balsam occurring at two high-elevation localities. The objective of the project described herein was to compile a checklist of all species of myxomycetes known to have been collected or observed in Shenandoah National Park in Virginia. Prior to the present study, just 10 species of myxomycetes had been collected in or reported as observations from the park. The checklist provided herein is based largely upon specimens collected by the two coauthors during the 2024 field season, but all previously known records or observations in the MyCoPortal database (MyCoPortal 2025) also are included.

Materials and Methods

In the present study, all specimens and samples for processing in moist chamber cultures were collected from areas adjacent to Skyline Drive. During visits to the field in 2024, substrates upon which the fruiting bodies of myxomycetes might be expected to occur were examined in an opportunistic manner as described by Cannon and Sutton (2004). Whenever the fruiting bodies were observed, the portion of the substrate upon which fruiting had occurred was collected and returned to the laboratory, where the fruiting bodies were dried at room temperature. Afterwards, pieces of the substrates with fruiting bodies present were glued to paper trays and the latter placed in small pasteboard boxes for permanent storage.

In addition to the field collections, samples of bark, ground litter, aerial litter, and other types of plant debris were collected. Trees from which samples of bark were collected included chestnut oak (*Quercus montana*), red oak (*Q. rubra*), black oak (*Q. velutina*), red cedar (*Juniperus virginiana*), dogwood (*Cornus florida*), ironwood (*Ostrya virginiana*), pitch pine (*Pinus pungens*), white pine (*P. strobus*), red spruce (*Picea rubens*), shadbush (*Amelanchier arborea*), black cherry (*Prunus serotina*), pignut hickory (*Carya glabra*), and shagbark hickory (*C. ovata*). Among the other plants providing samples of twigs, burs, inflorescences, aerial litter or ground litter to be processed in moist chamber cultures were summer grape (*Vitis aestivalis*), American chestnut (*Castanea dentata*), mountain laurel (*Kalmia latifolia*), goldenrod (*Solidago* spp.), blackberry (*Rubus* sp.), and Queen Anne's lace (*Daucus carota*).

All samples were returned to the laboratory and used to prepare moist chamber cultures in the manner described by Stephenson and Stempen (1994). Specimens appearing in these cultures were handled in the same manner as those collected in the field. All specimens of myxomycetes are deposited in the personal herbarium (SLS) of the first coauthor but ultimately will be transferred to the herbarium of Shenandoah National Park.

Results

More than 220 specimens of myxomycetes were collected in the field or obtained in moist chamber cultures. Most of these could be identified to the level of species, but a few were too aberrant for this to be possible. These specimens represented at least 69 different species in 26 genera. The nomenclature used follows Lado (2005-2025) except where noted. Recent molecular studies have resulted in a number of taxonomic rearrangements in the myxomycetes. As a result, some familiar species now have names that would not be immediately recognized by many of the people who collect and study myxomycetes.

Annotated List of Species

In the list that follows, all species of myxomycetes known to have been collected within or observed within Shenandoah National Park are arranged alphabetically by genus and then species. Information is provided on the source(s) of the record. Numbers given in parentheses are the collecting numbers of the first coauthor.

Angioridium sinuosum (Bull.) Grev.

Represented by two specimens (including SNP-223) appearing in moist chamber cultures on ground litter and old chestnut burs. In all but the most recent literature, this species is listed as *Physarum biforis* Pers.

Arcyria cinerea (Bull.) Pers.

Represented by eight specimens (including SNP-019 and SNP-117) appearing in moist chamber cultures on ground litter, twigs, grapevine bark, red spruce cones, chestnut burs, and chestnut oak bark along with six specimens (including SNP-091 and SNP-111) collected in the field from decaying wood. This is one of the most common of all myxomycetes and appears on all types of substrates in moist chamber cultures.

Arcyria denudata (L.) Wettst.

Represented by four specimens (including SNP-050) appearing in moist chamber cultures on twigs and shadbush bark along with four specimens (including SNP-168 and SNP-175) collected in the field from decaying wood. This species was first reported from the park based on a specimen observed in the field in 2016. The image that accompanied that observation appears to have been correctly identified.

Arcyria globosa Schein.

Represented by four specimens (including SNP-112) appearing in moist chamber cultures on old burs of American chestnut that had fallen from the tree. This species appears to have an unusual affinity for old chestnut burs and is rarely recorded on any other substrate. However, the author is aware of records from the burs of Allegheny chinquapin and Chinese chestnut.

Arcyria incarnata (Pers. ex. J.F. Gmel.) Pers.

Represented by 11 specimens (including SNP-106 and SNP-177) collected in the field from decaying wood.

Arcyria stipata (Schwein.) Lister

Represented by one specimen (SNP-162) collected in the field from decaying pine bark. Based on more than forty years of collecting by the first coauthor, this is a relatively rare species.

Brefeldia maxima (Fr.) Rostaf.

This species was first reported from the park based on two specimens observed in the field in 2016. The fruiting bodies of *Brefeldia maxima* are large and distinctive, but the dates (January) when the observations were made would be an unusual time of the year for any myxomycete to be fruiting. There are no images associated with these observations. As much, the occurrence of this species in the park is problematic.

Calomyxa metallica (Berk.) Nieuwl.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-141) appearing in a moist chamber culture on old, fallen red spruce cones.

Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa (O.F. Müll.) T. Macbr.

Represented by eight specimens (including SNP-059 and SNP-086) collected in the field on decaying wood. *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa* is not a “true” myxomycete and actually belongs to a sister group

of eumycetozoans (Fiore-Donno et al. 2010). However, it is usually collected or recorded in surveys for myxomycetes. This species was first reported from the park in 2016, based on a specimen observed in the field. *Ceratiomyxa fruticulosa* is exceedingly common in the park following a period of rain during the summer months.

Claustria didermoides (Pers.) Fr.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-054) appearing in a moist chamber culture on red cedar bark. In all but the most recent literature, this species is listed as *Physarum didermoides* (Pers.) Rostaf.

Clastoderma debaryanum A. Blytt

Represented by four specimens (including SNP-053) appearing in moist chamber cultures on twigs and leaf litter.

Collaria arcyronema (Rostaf.) Nann.-Bremek. ex Lado

Represented by five specimens (including SNP-047) appearing in moist chamber cultures on twigs and ground litter.

Collaria lurida (Lister) Nann.-Bremek.

Represented by two specimens (including SNP-113) appearing in moist chamber cultures on old burs of American chestnut that had fallen to the ground from the tree.

Colloderma oculatum (C. Lippert) G. Lister

Represented by one specimen (SNP-156) appearing in a moist chamber culture on grapevine bark.

Comatricha elegans (Racib.) G. Lister

Represented by one specimen (SNP-156) collected in the field from decaying wood.

Comatricha pulchella (C. Bab.) Rostaf.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-156) appearing in a moist chamber culture on ground litter.

Craterium leucocephalum (Pers. ex J.F. Gmel.) Ditmar

Represented by one specimen (SNP-230) appearing in a moist chamber culture on twigs.

Cribraria cancellata (Batsch) Nann.-Bremek.

Represented by three specimens (including SNP-073) collected in the field from decaying wood. In older books, this species is listed as *Dictydium cancellatum* (Batsch) T. Macbr.

Cribraria confusa Nann.-Bremek. & Y. Yamam.

Represented by two specimens (including SNP-009) appearing in moist chamber cultures on pine bark and woody twigs.

Cribraria microcarpa (Schrad.) Pers.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-230) appearing in a moist chamber culture on pine cone scales.

Cribraria minutissima Schwein.

Represented by three specimens (including SNP-008) appearing in moist chamber cultures on pitch pine bark and red oak bark.

***Cribraria violacea* Rex**

Represented by four specimens (including SNP-066) appearing in moist chamber cultures on red cedar bark. This species was first recorded from the park by K. H. McKnight in 1968, based on a specimen appearing in a moist chamber culture on willow bark. The specimen was identified by M. L. Farr. This is the only record of a myxomycete recorded from a moist chamber culture prior to the present study.

***Diderma chondrioderma* (de Bary & Rostaf.) Kuntze**

Represented by one specimen (SNP-134) appearing in a moist chamber culture on red cedar bark.

***Diderma deplanatum* Fr.**

Represented by two specimen (including SNP-216) appearing in moist chamber cultures on red cedar bark and white oak bark.

***Diderma effusum* (Schwein.) Morgan**

Represented by four specimens (including SNP-070 and SNP-145) appearing in moist chamber cultures on ground litter, chestnut oak bark, and black cherry bark.

***Diderma hemisphaericum* (Bull.) Hornem.**

Represented by six specimens (including SNP-070 and SNP-224) appearing in moist chamber cultures on chestnut oak bark, red oak bark, and black birch bark.

***Diderma platycarpum* Nann.-Bremek.**

Represented by one specimen (SNO-213) appearing in a moist chamber culture on red spruce twigs. This species is not recognized by all myxomycete taxonomists, who consider it synonymous with *Diderma saundersii*. However, the regular pattern of perforations in the fruiting body of *D. platycarpum* is not characteristic of *D. saundersii* (Mitchell 1999). *Diderma platycarpum* was recognized as a distinct species by Martin and Alexopoulos (1969).

***Diderma saundersii* (Berk. & Broome ex Masee) E. Sheld.**

Represented by four specimens (including SNP-052 and SNP-225) appearing in moist chamber cultures on twigs and shadbush bark.

***Didymium crustaceum* Peck**

This species was collected in the park in 1934 by C. L. Shear (BPI 815848) and identified by R. Hagelstein. The specimen is in the National Fungus Collections in Beltsville, Maryland.

***Didymium difforme* (Pers.) Gray**

Represented by two specimens (including SNP-197) appearing in moist chamber cultures on old inflorescences of *Daucus carota*.

***Didymium melanospermum* (Pers.) T. Macbr.**

This species was reported from the park in 1937, based on a specimen (BPI 816756) collected in the field and identified by R. Hagelstein.

***Didymium nigripes* (Link) Fr.**

Represented by two specimens, one (SNP-158) collected in the field from decaying wood and the other (SNP-128) appearing in a moist chamber culture on ground litter.

***Didymium squamulosum* (Alb. & Schwein.) Fr. & Palmquist**

Represented by six specimens (including SNP-133 and SNP-150) appearing in moist chamber cultures on ground litter and red spruce bark.

***Echinostelium minutum* de Bary**

Represented by five specimens (including SNP-013 and SNP-099) appearing in moist chamber cultures on pine bark and red cedar bark. The fruiting bodies of this tiny myxomycete are often abundant in the moist chamber cultures in which it occurs.

***Enerthenema papillatum* (Pers.) Rostaf.**

Represented by one specimen (SNP-101) appearing in a moist chamber culture on red spruce bark.

***Gulielmina vermicularis* (Schwein.) García-Cunch., J.C. Zamora & Lado**

Represented by four specimens (including SNP-005) appearing in moist chamber cultures on grapevine bark, twigs, and ironwood bark. In all but the most recent literature, this species is listed as *Perichaena vermicularis* (Schwein.) Rostaf.

***Hemitrichia calyculata* (Speg.) M.L. Farr**

Represented by five specimens (including SNP-164 and SNP-123) collected in the field on decaying wood.

***Hemitrichia clavata* (Pers.) Rostaf.**

Represented by four specimens (including SNP-167 and SNP-186) collected in the field on decaying wood.

***Hemitrichia serpula* (Scop.) Rostaf. ex Lister**

Represented by four specimens, with three of these (including SNP-067 and SNP-157) appearing in moist chamber cultures on ground litter and one (SNP-160) collected in the field on decaying wood. In the author's experience, *Hemitrichia serpula* is rarely recorded from moist chamber cultures.

***Heterotrichia obvelata* (Oeder) Yatsiuk, Leontyev & Schnittler**

Represented by one specimen (SNP-080) collected in the field from decaying wood. In all but the most recent literature, this species is listed as *Arcryia obvelata* (Oeder) Onsberg.

***Leocarpus fragilis* (Dicks.) Rostaf.**

Reported from the park in 1967, based on a specimen (BPI 813058) collected in the field and identified by M. L. Farr.

***Licea biforis* Morgan**

Represented by one specimen (SNP-208) appearing in a moist chamber culture on grapevine bark.

Licea minima Fr.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-46) appearing in a moist chamber culture on pitch pine bark.

Licea operculata (Wingate) G.W. Martin

Represented by two specimens (including SNP-006) appearing in moist chamber cultures of red oak bark.

Licea parasitica (Zukal) G.W. Martin

Represented by one specimen (SNP-155) appearing in a moist chamber culture on dogwood bark.

Licea rugosa Nann.-Bremek. & Y. Yamam.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-208) appearing in a moist chamber culture on red spruce bark.

Licea synsporos Nann.-Bremek.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-208) appearing on grapevine bark in a moist chamber culture. This species is distinguished from other species of *Licea* by its clustered spores. *Licea synsporos* appears to be very rare.

Lycogala epidendrum (L.) Fr.

Represented by 10 specimens (including SNP-060 and SNP-176) collected in the field on decaying wood and one specimen (SNP-205) appearing on a twig in a moist chamber culture. It is exceedingly rare for this species to appear in a moist chamber culture, but the unusually small aethalia are distinctive. It is now known that what has been recognized as the *Lycogala epidendrum* morphospecies actually consists of at least 60 biological species

Lycogala flavofuscum (Ehrenb.) Rostaf.

First reported from the park by R. W. Davidson in 1934 (BPI 834742 in the National Fungus Collections in Beltsville, Maryland). This species also was observed in the field during 2014. The fruiting bodies (aethalia) of *Lycogala flavofuscum* are large and distinctive, so there is no question about the identification being correct.

Macbrideola cornea (G. Lister & Cran) Alexop.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-221) appearing in a moist chamber culture on red spruce bark.

Macbrideola decapillata H.C. Gilbert

Represented by two specimens (SNP-037 and SNP-038) appearing in moist chamber cultures on red cedar bark.

Metatrachia vesparia (Batsch) Nann.-Bremek. ex G.W. Martin & Alexop.

Represented by three specimens (including SNP-125) appearing in moist chamber cultures on ground litter and decaying wood and nine specimens (including SNP094 and SNP-166) collected in the field on decaying wood.

Nannengaella globulifera (Bull.) J.M. García-Martin, J.C. Zamora & Lado

Represented by three specimens (including SNP-085) collected in the field from decaying wood. In all but the most recent literature, this species is listed as *Physarum globuliferum* (Bull.) Pers.

Oligonema favogineum (Batsch) García-Cunch., J.C. Zamora & Lado

Represented by one specimen (SNP-208) appearing in a moist chamber culture on grapevine bark. In all but the most recent literature, this species is listed as *Trichia favoginea* (Batsch) Pers.

Ophiotheca chrysosperma Curr.

Represented by two specimens, with one (SNP-202) collected from decaying wood and the other (SNP-033) appearing in a moist chamber culture on a twig. In all but the most recent literature, this species is listed as *Perichaena chrysosperma* (Curr.) Lister.

Ophiotheca pedata (Lister & G. Lister) García-Cunch., J.C. Zamora & Lado

Represented by one specimen (SNP-124) appearing in a moist chamber culture on red cedar bark. In all but the most recent literature, this species is listed as *Perichaena pedata* (Lister & G. Lister) G. Lister ex E. Jahn.

Paradiacheopsis solitaria (Nann.-Bremek.) Nann.-Bremek.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-215) appearing in a moist chamber culture on red spruce bark.

Perichaena depressa Lib.

Represented by two specimens (including SNP-043) appearing in moist chamber cultures on red cedar bark.

Physarum album (Bull.) Chevall.

Represented by six specimens (including SNP-144 and SNP-199) appearing in moist chamber cultures on white pine bark and two specimens (SNP-075 and SNP-081) collected in the field from decaying wood.

Physarum cinereum (Batsch) Pers.

Represented by two specimens (SNP-004 and SNP-223) appearing in moist chamber cultures on aerial litter and an inflorescence.

Physarum crateriforme Petch

Represented by two specimens (SNP-036 and SNP-014) appearing in moist chamber cultures on red cedar bark.

Physarum decipiens M.A. Curtis

Represented by three specimens (including SNP-028) recorded from moist chamber cultures and one specimen (SNP-159) collected in the field on grapevine bark.

Physarum galbeum Wingate

Represented by two specimens (including SNP-208) appearing in moist chamber cultures on pine cone scales.

Physarum pusillum (Berk. & M.A. Curtis) G. Lister

Represented by one specimen (SNP-138) appearing in a moist chamber culture on red spruce bark.

Physarum cf. vernum Sommerf.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-143) appearing in a moist chamber culture on red cedar bark. This specimen keys out to *Physarum vernum* but that identification appears to be problematic. However, this specimen is clearly different from any other species of *Physarum* recorded from Shenandoah National Park.

Physarum viride (Bull.) Pers.

Represented by five specimens (including SNP-092 and SNP-174) collected in the field on decaying wood.

Reticularia splendens Morgan

Represented by two specimens (SNP-170 and SNP-178) collected in the field on decaying wood. The aethalia for both specimens were unusually small for this species. This appeared very late in the field season.

Stemonitis axifera (Bull.) T. Macbr.

Represented by three specimens (including SNP-087) collected in the field from decaying wood.

Stemonitis fusca Roth

Represented by one specimen (SNP-084) collected from a decaying red spruce log.

Stemonitis nigrescens Rex

Represented by six specimens (including SNP-035 and SNP-154) appearing in moist chamber cultures on twigs. One specimen (SNP-228) was collected from an aerial twig. *Stemonitis nigrescens* has not always been recognized as distinct from *S. fusca*. Both Martin and Alexopoulos (1969) and Ing (1999) did recognize *S. nigrescens*. The latter author pointed out that the two species are biologically different, with *S. nigrescens* appearing in moist chamber cultures while this is not typically the case for *S. fusca*.

Stemonitis smithii T. Macbr.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-180) collected in the field from decaying wood. Like *Stemonitis nigrescens*, *S. smithii* is not always regarded as distinct from another species—in this case *Stemonitis axifera*. However, *S. smithii* was recognized by both Martin and Alexopoulos (1969) and Ing (1999). In the experience of the author, this species is not common, but the small fruiting bodies, typically occurring in small clusters, distinguish *S. smithii* from *S. axifera*.

Stemonitopsis gracilis (G. Lister) Nann.-Bremek.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-093) collected in the field from decaying wood.

Stemonitopsis hyperopta (Meyl.) Nann.-Bremek.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-088) collected in the field from decaying wood.

Stemonitopsis typhina (F.H. Wigg.) Nann.-Bremek.

First reported from the park by C. L. Shear in 1936. The specimen (BPI 822858) was identified by R. L. Hagelstein.

Trichia contorta (Ditmar) Rostaf.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-034) appearing in a moist chamber culture on pine bark.

Trichia munda (Lister) Meyl.

Represented by four specimens (including SNP-011) appearing in moist chamber cultures on chestnut oak bark.

Trichia subfusca Rex

Represented by two specimens (including SNP-142) appearing in moist chamber cultures on ground litter.

Trichia varia (Pers. ex J.F. Gmel.) Pers.

Represented by one specimen (SNP-187) collected in the field from decaying wood.

Tubifera ferruginosa (Batsch) Gmelin

Reported from the park based on five specimens observed in the field during the period of 2010 to 2014. All observations were of immature pseudoaethalia in the “red” stage of development. The fruiting bodies of *Tubifera ferruginosa* are large and distinctive, so there is no question about the identification being correct.

Discussion

The 2024 field season in the general study area was unusually dry. Because collecting in the field was not particularly productive, the primary focus of the study reported herein was on collecting substrates (e.g., bark, twigs, ground litter, and aerial litter) that could be processed in moist chamber cultures. The author has prepared thousands of moist chamber cultures over his career, and the bark samples collected in Shenandoah National Park yielded far fewer myxomycetes (both the total number of fruiting bodies and the number of species) than any comparable set of samples he has ever processed for any region of the temperate zone. It is unknown why this was the case, but both 2023 and 2024 were unusually dry. Substrates other than bark also were not consistently productive for myxomycetes. Nevertheless, the list of myxomycetes known from Shenandoah National Park is now seventy-nine species despite the absence of some species that almost surely occur in the park but have yet to be recorded. Prominent examples include *Badhamia utricularis*, *Comatricha nigra*, *Cribraria intricata*, *Diachea leucopodia*, *Fuligo septica*, and *Lamproderma scintillans*.

The absence of the species listed above is evidence of the fact that any survey for myxomycetes limited to a single field season cannot possibly be complete. A survey encompassing multiple years would yield more species, but because some species of myxomycetes are truly rare or simply do not form fruiting bodies in a particular year it still would not be complete. It is likely that the moist chamber component of the present study captured more of the biodiversity of the assemblage of species present in the park than the field collecting component. However, for the former, the range of substrates examined was incomplete, so there are certainly additional species yet to be recorded. For example, some small populations of naturally occurring red spruce and balsam fir (*Abies balsamea*) occur at two of the highest elevations in the park. No visits were made to either of the sites where these two trees are found. The primary value of

the survey carried out during the 2024 field season is that it provides a baseline of data as a starting point for future studies.

Acknowledgements

Field work in Shenandoah National Park was carried out under the authorization of collecting permit SHEN-2024-SCI-0013.

References

- Cannon P, Sutton B. 2004. Microfungi on wood and plant debris. In: Mueller G, Bills G., Foster M, editors. Biodiversity of Fungi: Inventory and Monitoring Methods. Massachusetts: Elsevier Academic Press. p. 217-239.
- Fiore-Donno AM, Nikolaev SI, Nelson M, Pawlowski J, Cavalier-Smith T, Baldauf SL. 2010. Deep phylogeny and evolution of slime moulds (Mycetozoa). *Protist* 161: 55-70.
- Ing, B. 1999. *The Myxomycetes of Britain and Ireland: An Identification Handbook*. England: Richmond Publishing.
- Lado C [Internet]. 2005-2025. An on-line nomenclatural information system of Eumycetozoa, Madrid: Real Jardín Botánico de Madrid, CSIC; [visited 10 Apr 2025]. Available from: <http://www.eumycetozoa.com>
- Martin GW, Alexopoulos CJ. 1969. *The Myxomycetes*. Iowa City: University of Iowa Press.
- Mitchell, D. 1999. *Diderma platycarpum* var. *platycarpum*, a new British record. *Mycologist* 13: 112.
- MyCoPortal [Internet]. 2024. USA: National Science Foundation; [visited 31 Dec 2024]. Available from: <http://www.mycportal.org>
- Stephenson SL, Stempen H. 1994. *Myxomycetes: A Handbook of Slime Molds*. Oregon: Timber Press.